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Study of the over-response of radiochromic films in ultra-high dose rate and dose per pulse electron beams

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Abstract

Objective. Many pre-clinical experiments on FLASH radiotherapy, in which biological samples are irradiated at conventional and ultra-high dose rate (UHDR), make use of radiochromic films as an absolute dose reference because their response is typically assumed to be dose rate independent. While several previous experiments confirmed this assumption, a recent study with protons found an over-response for Gafchromic EBT3 films at UHDR (Villoing *et al* 2022 *Med. Phys.* **49** 2732–45). If EBT3 is used as a reference in FLASH experiments, the over-response could result in an underdosing that falsely appears as sparing of normal tissue. **Approach.** To investigate whether the reported dose rate dependence of EBT3 can be reproduced with UHDR electron radiation as well, about 600 EBT3 samples were irradiated at the metrological linear accelerator facility at Physikalisch Technische Bundesanstalt, Braunschweig, and at the ELBE research accelerator at Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf, with different beam parameters. As dosimetric reference served a PTW flashDiamond detector which has been verified to show no deviation in the studied UHDR range as well as Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt's alanine dosimetry system. In addition, several OC-1 films, which have been shown to be dose rate independent in previous studies, were irradiated together with EBT3 films. **Main results.** EBT3 shows a significant over-response at ultra-high dose per pulse and intra-pulse dose rates. Up to 3 Gy per pulse no significant deviations were observed. However, for larger doses per pulse an over-response was observed that increases with dose per pulse to up to 50%. For OC-1 films no significant effects were found. **Significance.** We provide evidence for the over-response of EBT3 films in UHDR electron beams. Therefore, EBT3 films should be used with caution in FLASH experiments.

1. Introduction

The discovery of the FLASH effect, the sparing of normal tissue at the same tumor treatment efficiency when applying a ultra-high dose rate (UHDR) as compared to low conventional dose rates (Favaudon *et al* 2014), has stimulated radiobiology and radiochemistry research at many centers worldwide. The UHDR required to observe the FLASH effect *in vivo* has also turned out to be a challenge for accurate dosimetry (Schüller *et al* 2020, Romano *et al* 2022). In FLASH experiments, the dosimetry needs to be accurate for the ultra-high (typically $>40\text{Gys}^{-1}$) and the low (conventional) dose rate used as reference (typically in the order of a few Gymin^{-1}). The single fraction dose required to observe the FLASH effect is typically above 7 Gy (Böhlen *et al* 2022). This high single fraction dose can either be

applied with a few intense pulses with doses of a few Gy, as typically delivered by electron linacs, or with a single continuous beam pulse as e.g. delivered by isochronous cyclotrons. Ionization chambers, the gold standard for dosimetry in radiotherapy and radiobiology, show considerable deviations as a result of charge losses due to ion recombination at ultra-high dose per pulse, and are therefore only suitable to a limited extent for dosimetry for irradiations with strongly pulsed beams such as those delivered by UHDR electron linear accelerators. Many pre-clinical and radiobiological experiments on the topic of FLASH radiotherapy make use of radiochromic films, most commonly EBT3 (Gafchromic, Ashland Advanced Materials, Bridgewater, USA), as dosimetric reference (Giannini *et al* 2024, DeFrancisco and Kim 2025). DeFrancisco and Kim (2025) even concluded that Gafchromic films are the most frequently used detector in electron FLASH studies. They are typically based on a radiation sensitive monomer that is incorporated into a water-soluble polymer matrix coated onto a polyester base and when irradiated they show a dose-dependent color change due to radiation-induced polymerization. Besides the relative 2D information provided by radiochromic films they can also be calibrated in terms of absolute dose (Devic 2011, Liu *et al* 2023). Their response is typically believed to be dose rate independent in the range relevant for FLASH radiotherapy (Romano *et al* 2022) and therefore they have been applied in many FLASH experiments to adjust or to verify the absolute dose output at UHDR (Lempart *et al* 2019, Konradsson *et al* 2020, 2021, Garty *et al* 2022, Xie *et al* 2022). While several previous experiments supported this assumption (Jaccard *et al* 2017, Favaudon *et al* 2019, Jorge *et al* 2019, Togno *et al* 2022), a recent study with protons by Villoing *et al* (2022) found a significant response enhancement for EBT3 and EBT-XD films at UHDR, i.e. at doses per pulse above 10 Gy at an intra-pulse dose rate of 7.5 kGys^{-1} . Very recently, also (Cayley *et al* 2025, Del Sarto *et al* 2025 and Yasuda *et al* 2026) found indications for an over-response of EBT-XD films in experiments with UHDR electrons and protons as well. Such a dose rate dependence would make the suitability of this type of films as reference in radiobiological FLASH experiments highly questionable if not corrected for. The over-response of the radiochromic films at UHDR as found by Villoing *et al* (2022) would result in an underdosing that could falsely appear as sparing of normal tissue. That could make the FLASH effect seem stronger than it actually is or could even give the impression of a FLASH effect when in reality there is no difference in the biological response at UHDR at all. Notably, the magnitude of the over-response of EBT3 films at UHDR reported by Villoing *et al* (2022) at an UHDR of 7.5 kGys^{-1} is in the order of the FLASH effect itself ($\sim 20\%$) (Böhlen *et al* 2022). For the up to now rarely utilized OC-1 films (OrthoChromic, Hillsborough, NJ, USA) (Lim and Tang 2022) no dose rate dependence was found by Villoing *et al* (2022). The radiation-induced polymerization reaction in EBT3 films creates macromolecules with a pre-determined orientation. Therefore, these films show different light absorption characteristics depending on their orientation to the film scanner (Schoenfeld *et al* 2014). In addition to the above mentioned response enhancement, Yasuda *et al* (2025) also found changes in the orientation effects of EBT3 films irradiated with UHDR proton beams as compared to irradiations at low dose rate.

To investigate whether the over-response of EBT3 can also be reproduced with electron beams and which beam parameters it depends on, extensive experiments were conducted at two different electron linear accelerator facilities. Approximately 600 EBT3 film samples were irradiated over a wide range of dose rates and doses per pulse. Three different independent reference detectors were applied: A flashDiamond (fD), alanine pellets as well as OC-1 films.

2. Material and methods

Four different measurement campaigns were conducted at two different electron accelerator facilities with different UHDR ranges and beam structures. Specific emphasis was put on the use of suitable and independent reference detectors to compare the radiochromic film response to:

- (i) EBT3 vs flashDiamond (total doses in the range of 3 – 100 Gy, at five different doses per pulse in the range between 0.1 and 18.5 Gy, at a pulse duration of $2 \mu\text{s}$)
- (ii) EBT3 vs flashDiamond and alanine (total doses around 15 – 20 Gy where the uncertainties of the used alanine system are minimal, at doses per pulse in the range 0.3 – 20 Gy, at a pulse duration of $1 \mu\text{s}$ or $2 \mu\text{s}$)
- (iii) EBT3 vs flashDiamond and OC-1 (total doses around 30 Gy, at doses per pulse in the range between 0.3 and 33 Gy, at a pulse duration of $2 \mu\text{s}$)
- (iv) EBT3 vs flashDiamond and OC-1 (irradiation with single pulses at different intra-pulse dose rates between 0.16 Gys^{-1} and 90 kGys^{-1} , variation of the pulse durations leading to doses per pulse in the range between 5 – 100 Gy)

Campaigns (i)–(iii) were conducted at the metrological linear accelerator facility at the Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB) in Braunschweig, Germany, and (iv) at the Electron Linear accelerator with high Brilliance and low Emittance (ELBE) at Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR), Dresden, Germany. In the following, more details on the different measurement campaigns are given.

2.1. Irradiation experiments at the metrological electron linac at PTB

Experiments were conducted at the metrological electron linear accelerator facility at PTB. A medical linear accelerator (Elekta Synergy) and a research electron accelerator at PTB were used. Both accelerators deliver a pulsed electron beam with a pulse duration of a few microseconds, consisting of a train of electron bunches with a repetition rate of 3 GHz. This is a similar pulse structure as that found in linacs used in clinics for research on FLASH radiotherapy with electrons (e.g. Mobetron, FLASHknife, SIT ElectronFlash (Marinelli *et al* 2022), converted medical linacs). EBT3 and OC-1 film samples (size: $40 \times 35 \text{ mm}^2$) were irradiated with electron pulses (20 MeV, $2 \mu\text{s}$ macro pulse duration) over a wide range of total doses (3.5 – 100 Gy) with different intra-pulse dose rates (55 kGys^{-1} – 16.5 MGys^{-1}). The films were irradiated in a water phantom at the depth of maximum dose (30.8 mm). Up to three films were stacked on top of each other and irradiated at the same time in order to increase the measurement statistics. For the majority of the irradiations, the pulse duration was kept constant at $2 \mu\text{s}$ and the dose per pulse was varied via the intra-pulse dose rate, either by varying the charge per pulse provided by the electron gun, or by adding Aluminum scattering discs (thickness 6, 2 or 1 mm) at the vacuum exit window of the beamline, or by changing the source to surface distance (SSD) between 90, 70, or 50 cm. In measurement campaign (ii) the dose per pulse was varied by lowering the pulse duration while keeping the intra-pulse dose rate constant in order to disentangle the influence of intra-pulse dose rate and dose per pulse. The films were irradiated with a different number of pulses at a pulse repetition frequency of 5 Hz. At this frequency the individual pulses can be considered as independent for detectors based on radiochemical principles such as radiochromic films. For example, at a dose per pulse of 0.06 Gy, 500 pulses were required to irradiate the film with a total dose of 30 Gy, whereas at 30 Gy per pulse, only a single pulse was delivered. As dosimetric reference served a flashDiamond detector (model 60 025, serial number 7610, PTW dosimetry, Freiburg, Germany) that had previously been extensively characterized in this UHDR electron beam, demonstrating a linear response compared with alanine (see figure 1). In measurement campaign (ii), alanine was directly irradiated together with EBT3 films as an another dose rate independent reference (Soliman *et al* 2020, Bourgouin *et al* 2022) in addition to the flashDiamond. The alanine dosimetry system has been shown to be consistent with the PTB water calorimeter primary standard also under ultra-high dose per pulse conditions (Bourgouin *et al* 2023).

For all measurement campaigns at PTB ((i) – (iii)), an integrating current transformer (Bergoz Instrumentation, Saint Genis Pouilly, France, ICT in-flange version, turns ratio 50:1) was used to monitor precisely ($\pm 0.1\%$) the charge of the electron pulses (30–300 nC) (Schüller *et al* 2017). For each setup with respect to SSD, scattering disc and pulse duration, the beam pulse charge was varied and recorded as function of the simultaneously determined dose per pulse, measured by means of the calibrated flash-Diamond at the same water depths as chosen for the positioning of the EBT3 films. Calibration functions were then fitted to the data sets, which allowed to convert the measured ICT signal to the actual dose per pulse during the irradiation of the films with low uncertainty ($< 1\%$).

Figure 2(a) shows a schematic of the experimental setup at PTB. The electron beam passes through the ICT before exiting the vacuum through a Titanium window and being scattered by Aluminum plates. The water phantom is positioned at a variable distance from the scatterer to realize different doses per pulse. The radiochromic films and the alanine holder are positioned at $\sim 3 \text{ cm}$ water equivalent depth.

2.2. Irradiation experiments at ELBE research electron linac

In measurement campaign (iv) experiments with a different dose per pulse and dose rate range (5 – 95 Gy per pulse at 1000 Gys^{-1} , 10000 Gys^{-1} and 90000 Gys^{-1}) were performed at the ELBE electron accelerator (Gabriel *et al* 2000) using 30 MeV electrons, where several radiobiological FLASH experiments have been performed in the past (Pawelke *et al* 2021, Karsch *et al* 2022, Horst *et al* 2023, 2024). All irradiations at ELBE were performed with single pulses, where each pulse was a bunch train consisting of $\sim 5 \text{ ps}$ electron bunches separated by 77 ns pauses (bunch repetition rate: 13 MHz). The dose rate was adjusted by varying the bunch charge and the dose per pulse was set by varying the number of bunches and thus the pulse duration (length of the bunch train). The lowest dose rate used was in the order of $10 \text{ Gymin}^{-1} \approx 0.16 \text{ Gys}^{-1}$. The films were irradiated in air as stacks of EBT3 and OC-1 films (size: $48 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$). Reference measurements were performed beforehand for every dose per pulse and dose rate setting with a flashDiamond (serial number 220 517) right behind the film position positioned at

Figure 1. flashDiamond (SN7601) dose reading compared to alanine reference as a function of dose per pulse (DPP) and intra-pulse dose rate obtained in experiments at the PTB metrological electron linear accelerator.

Figure 2. Experimental setup at the research electron linac at PTB (a) and at the ELBE accelerator (b). In the PTB setup, the films and alanine can be replaced by a flashDiamond measuring at the same water depth like the films. The dimensions are not true to scale.

the maximum of the beam spot (Gaussian profile with a $\pm 5\%$ homogeneity over a diameter of 6.5 mm). The readings of the flashDiamond were used to calibrate a transmission ionization chamber (model 7862, PTW Dosimetry, Freiburg, Germany) used as beam monitor for each dose rate and dose per pulse setting.

Figure 2(b) shows a schematic of the experimental setup at ELBE. The electron beam exits the vacuum through a Beryllium window and is scattered by a thin PMMA plate before passing through a

Figure 3. Panel (a): Intra-pulse dose rate and pulse duration at irradiation with 20 Gy per pulse at the research electron linac at PTB compared to the 90 kGy s^{-1} dose rate setting of the ELBE accelerator. Panel (b): Bunch time structure of the two electron beams.

Figure 4. flashDiamond (SN220517) dose reading as a function of the number of electron bunches per pulse obtained in experiments at the ELBE accelerator with its highest dose rate setting.

transmission ionization chamber. The sample holder which can hold the flashDiamond with the films stuck on top is positioned some centimeters downstream.

Notably, the electron accelerators at PTB and the ELBE research accelerator have very different time structures as shown in figure 3. The electron beam at PTB is strongly pulsed with $1 - 2 \mu\text{s}$ macro pulse duration with 3 GHz accelerating radiofrequency and therefore comparable to FLASH electron linacs that are available for potential clinical applications. The ELBE electron beam, on the other hand, can provide much longer macro pulses (up to seconds or even minutes) which are trains of 5 ps bunches divided by pauses of 77 ns duration (corresponding to 13 MHz bunch repetition frequency).

It was verified beforehand that the flashDiamond detector provides reliable dose readings in the ELBE beam since it has not been tested under similar conditions before. Figure 4 shows the dose reading of the flashDiamond as a function of the number of electron bunches at maximum bunch charge for a measurement series where the length of the bunch train, i.e. the pulse length, was gradually increased while keeping the intra-pulse dose rate constant at 90 kGy s^{-1} . The flashDiamond response increases linear with the number of bunches in the pulse as expected and no saturation behavior is observed even at the highest dose per pulse of almost 100 Gy. Therefore, the flashDiamond was found suitable

for dosimetry in the electron beam of the ELBE accelerator and could be applied as reference for the radiochromic film studies.

2.3. Radiochromic films

For the experiments at PTB (measurement campaigns (i)–(iii)), the films were immersed in water while at ELBE (measurement campaign (iv)) they were irradiated free in air. In order to increase the measurements statistics, the films were arranged as stacks consisting of three EBT3 films or one OC-1 film in the front and two EBT3 films behind (at PTB) or one OC-1 film in the front and three EBT3 films behind (at ELBE). The films were all from the same production batch (EBT3 films: LOT 11 192 002, OC-1 films: LOT # 2-2020 507-2). EBT3 films were scanned 48–72 h after irradiation. OC-1 films were scanned 10 d after irradiation because of their considerably slower darkening as compared to EBT3 films (Lim and Tang 2022, Villoing *et al* 2022). An Expression 11 000 XL scanner (Epson, Suwa, Japan) was used for scanning all films. The films were oriented in landscape orientation for all scans. From the red-green-blue images, both the red and green channel were analyzed for EBT3 films and only the green channel for OC-1. For evaluation of the doses the netOD, defined as $\text{netOD} = -\log_{10}(\text{OD}_D/\text{OD}_{0\text{Gy}})$ with OD_D being the optical density of the irradiated film and $\text{OD}_{0\text{Gy}}$ being the optical density of an unirradiated film of the same sheet, was analyzed. EBT3 films were calibrated at the Elekta Synergy linac at PTB operated in 18 MeV electron mode at conventional dose rate ($\sim 5 \text{ Gy min}^{-1}$) by relating the netOD to the absorbed dose to water determined with a reference ionization chamber (Roos Electron Chamber, model 34 001, PTW Dosimetry, Freiburg, Germany). This ionization chamber is directly traceable to the German primary standard of absorbed dose to water. OC-1 films were always irradiated together with EBT3 films. Therefore, the OC-1 films were cross-calibrated using the EBT3 data obtained at low dose rate at the PTB research linac (measurement campaigns (i)–(iii)) or the ELBE accelerator (measurement campaign (iv)), respectively.

Some EBT3 films were also scanned with an ArtixScan 2500f (Microtek, Hsinchu, Taiwan) scanner at PTB and some OC-1 films also with a Perfection V850 Pro (Epson, Suwa, Japan) scanner at Institute Gustave Roussy. This was done because different scanners have different calibration functions when used for film dosimetry and by using multiple scanner models possible influences of the scanner used can be excluded. Furthermore, at Institute Gustave Roussy the OC-1 film type was already in use previously and therefore the analysis could be done with an established dosimetry system.

The radiation fields applied have Gaussian lateral profiles (2.8 cm FWHM at ELBE and 28.8 – 4.17 cm FWHM, depending on the setup, at PTB). The dose maximum of the 2D dose distributions on the films was analyzed and consequently the reference detectors were positioned at the dose maximum as well.

3. Results

3.1. Experiments at PTB

Figure 5 shows the EBT3 calibration functions obtained for the red and green color channels obtained from calibration with conventional dose rates (0.2 mGy per pulse) at the Elekta Synergy linac at PTB for two different scanners (Epson 11 000 XL and Microtek ArtixScan 2500f). Using the Epson 11 000 XL scanner, the red channel can only be used to evaluate doses up to ~ 20 Gy. At the increased optical density at higher doses, the Epson 11 000 XL can hardly distinguish between the different degrees of darkening and the netOD value is almost independent on the dose and saturates at a value of 1.2. However, the Microtek ArtixScan 2500f is still sensitive at higher optical densities (netOD values > 1.2). The slope of the calibration function and thus the sensitivity to dose differences decreases with increasing dose, yet this scanner still allows evaluation of the red channel for dosimetry up to 100 Gy, which is far beyond the dose range specified by the vendor (0.01 – 10 Gy). This aligns with recent updated recommendations on the use of EBT3 films by Liu *et al* (2023) who found it suitable up to 50 Gy. By analyzing the green channel of EBT3 films scanned with the EPSON 11 000 XL scanner, they can be applied for dosimetry up to 100 Gy also using this scanner, as seen in figure 5(a). In addition to the calibration curves obtained by reference irradiations at the Elekta Synergy medical linac, also values obtained by the results from EBT3 irradiation at the PTB research electron linac operating at 0.1 Gy per $2 \mu\text{s}$ pulse and at UHDR of 18.5 Gy per $2 \mu\text{s}$ pulse are shown in figure 5. The netOD values obtained at 0.1 Gy per pulse agree well with those obtained from irradiation with conventional dose rates at the Elekta linac used for determining the calibration function. However, it can be noticed that the data points representing the results from EBT3 irradiation with 18.5 Gy per pulse lie all above the calibration function, and therefore it is evident that the EBT3 films show an over-response.

The EBT3 dose readings relative to the flashDiamond used as reference for the irradiations at the PTB research linac are shown for the red channel in figure 6(a) (only total doses up to 20 Gy for the Epson 11 000 XL) and for the green channel in figure 6(b).

For the lowest dose per pulse studied (0.1 Gy/pulse), the average relative response lies at 1 which means that the films behave exactly like during the calibration at the Elekta Synergy linac operated with conventional dose rate. Towards higher doses per pulse the average relative response deviates from 1 and increases up to ~ 1.15 at 18.5 Gy per pulse, indicating a 15% over-response. For the green channel, a significant difference from 1 can be observed for doses per pulse above 8.3 Gy. The over-response effect seems to be equally pronounced in both color channels. The values at 18.5 Gy/pulse obtained with the two different scanners are also in good agreement with each other. Furthermore, no dependence of the over-response on the total dose at the same dose per pulse was observed.

Figure 7 shows data from measurement campaign (ii) performed at the PTB electron research linac where EBT3 films were irradiated together with alanine (Bourgouin *et al* 2022). Figure 7(a) shows the ratio of the flashDiamond dose reading to the alanine reference as a function of dose per pulse and no significant variation from 1 can be observed. This proves the suitability of the flashDiamond detector as dose rate independent reference.

In contrast to this, the EBT3 readings relative to the alanine reference as a function of dose per pulse shown in figure 7(b) exhibit an over-response that increases with increasing dose per pulse. Figure 7(c) shows the same data points as in figure 7(b) but as a function of intra-pulse dose rate. One can observe that the orange data points, where the intra-pulse dose rate was kept constant but the dose per pulse was reduced by halving the pulse duration, only align with the fitted function for the other data points

Figure 6. EBT3 dose reading (red channel) (a) and EBT3 dose reading (green channel) (b) relative to the flashDiamond (fD) reference as a function of dose per pulse (measurement campaign (i)). The second x-axis label shows the intra-pulse dose rate in the $2\ \mu\text{s}$ pulses from the electron linac. The films irradiated with the highest dose per pulse (18.5 Gy/pulse) were analyzed with two different scanners (Epson 11 000 XL, red dots, and Microtek ArtixScan 2500f, black triangles).

Figure 7. Panel (a): flashDiamond (fD) dose reading relative to the alanine reference as a function of dose per pulse (measurement campaign (ii)). Panel (b): EBT3 dose reading (green channel) relative to the alanine reference as a function of dose per pulse. Panel (c): Same data as in (b) but as a function of intra-pulse dose rate. The orange symbols represent irradiations with $1\ \mu\text{s}$ pulse duration and the blue symbols irradiations with the same intra-pulse dose rates but with $1.9\ \mu\text{s}$ pulse duration. The black circles represent all other data points, which were obtained with a fixed pulse duration of $1.9\ \mu\text{s}$.

when plotted as a function of dose per pulse (figure 7(b)). Notably, these measurements with variation of the pulse duration were performed directly after another without changing anything related to the experimental conditions.

Figure 8 shows data from measurement campaign (iii), also performed at the PTB electron research linac, where EBT3 films were irradiated together with OC1 films with total doses around 30 Gy. Since no dependence of the over-response of EBT3 on the total dose or the color channel was found in the previous experiments only 30 Gy was used, the dose range where the green channel has an optimum sensitivity. In this experiment, OC-1 films were included as well since Villoing *et al* (2022) suggested them as a dose rate independent alternative to EBT3.

Figure 8(a) shows the EBT3 dose reading relative to the flashDiamond reference as a function of dose per pulse. A deviation from 1 can be observed for 3 Gy per pulse and above and at 7 Gy per pulse the mean deviation is already at 6%. Notably, for the highest dose per pulse of 32.5 Gy, the observed over-response is around 25%. As shown in figure 8(b), for OC-1 films irradiated together with the EBT3

films, no over-response or other trend can be observed in our data which confirms the findings by Villoing *et al* (2022) from their experiments with continuous proton beams.

3.2. Experiments at ELBE accelerator

In addition to the experiments at the PTB research linac (measurement campaigns (i)–(iii)), providing microsecond electron pulses with intra-pulse dose rates in the MGys^{-1} range, we also performed experiments at the ELBE research accelerator (measurement campaign (iv)) which offers a different beam parameter range.

While the highest dose per pulse that could be reached at the PTB linac was 32.5 Gy, at the ELBE accelerator the studied range could be extended up to more than 90 Gy in a single pulse. Figure 9(a) shows the film reading relative to the flashDiamond reference as a function of dose per pulse obtained for EBT3 films at different intra-pulse dose rates and figure 9(b) shows the corresponding data for OC-1 films irradiated together with the EBT3 films at lowest and highest intra-pulse dose rates used. At 0.16Gys^{-1} , which is in the order of magnitude of the average dose rate of conventional radiotherapy devices, no significant trend with increasing dose per pulse can be observed for EBT3 nor for OC-1. However, at 90kGys^{-1} , the EBT3 films show an over-response that increases together with the dose per pulse. For an intermediate intra-pulse dose rate of 10kGys^{-1} the EBT3 over-response is still apparent but less pronounced than for 90kGys^{-1} . At an intra-pulse dose rate of 1kGys^{-1} , however, the effect disappears and the EBT3 response is again identical to that observed at conventional dose rate.

It is noticeable in figure 9 that the ELBE data points scatter much more compared to the data measured at PTB (figures 6–8). The setup and the experimental conditions at ELBE do not offer a precision

Figure 10. Panel (a): Linear model describing the relative EBT3 reading as a function of dose per pulse for the three intra-pulse dose rates where an over-response was observed. Panel (b): Model parameter m as a function of intra-pulse dose rate.

that is as good as the setup at PTB. In the irradiation setup at ELBE, the flashDiamond used as reference is placed inside a sample holder immersed with water leading to a water equivalent measurement depth difference of about 10 mm (see figure 2(b)). The radiochromic films were stuck on the front face of such sample holders and therefore the flashDiamond measured at a slightly larger depth and distance compared to the films. However, the over-response effect in the ELBE beam is so strongly pronounced that it is still clearly evident, despite the less defined setup as compared to the experiments at PTB.

4. Discussion

The data set shown in figures 5 and 6 confirms the findings by Villoing *et al* (2022) and clearly shows that the over-response of EBT3 films at UHDR observed in their experiments with single pulses of continuous proton beams can also be reproduced with electron beams. However, from the data in figures 5 and 6 one can not yet differentiate if the dose per pulse or the intra-pulse dose rate is the driving factor behind the EBT3 film over-response. Therefore, another experiment (measurement campaign (ii)) was conducted where for some irradiations the pulse duration was halved while the intra-pulse dose rate was kept constant (see figure 7). The results of these measurements show that the dose per pulse rather than the intra-pulse dose rate seems to be the crucial parameter that determines the magnitude of the EBT3 over-response. However, the following experiments performed at the ELBE accelerator revealed that the intra-pulse dose rate seems to play a role as well (see figure 9). We hypothesize that a certain combination of intra-pulse dose rate and dose per pulse is necessary for the effect to occur, which would explain why it did not appear in previous studies and was discovered only recently. Our results indicate that up to intra-pulse dose rates of about 1 kGys^{-1} and doses per pulse up to about 2 Gy EBT3 films can be safely applied while at higher dose rates or dose per pulse one should be cautious. That is in agreement with the results by Villoing *et al* (2022) who found only minor effects at 1.5 kGys^{-1} while at 7.5 kGys^{-1} they observed an over-response with a magnitude that is quantitatively comparable to the data for 10 kGys^{-1} presented in this work.

The data measured at the PTB research linac and at the ELBE accelerator were analyzed together to better understand the over-response of EBT3 films for certain combinations of intra-pulse dose rate and dose per pulse.

Figure 10(a) shows the EBT3 dose reading relative to the flashDiamond reference as a function of dose per pulse for the three intra-pulse dose rates where a over-response was observed (same data sets as shown in figures 8 and 9) together with linear fit functions of the form $y = m \cdot x + 1$ where y is the relative response and x is the dose per pulse in Gy. Figure 10(b) shows the parameter m as a function of intra-pulse dose rate DR (in Gys^{-1}). For the PTB irradiations, the intra-pulse dose rate was varied to change the dose per pulse, therefore, an average value of $DR = 10 \pm 5\text{ MGys}^{-1}$ is used for the plot in figure 10(b). This systematic representation of the EBT3 over-response data shows that the over-response is determined by both the dose per pulse and by the intra-pulse dose rate. For higher intra-pulse dose rates the over-response effect is more pronounced. The functions in figure 10(a) can, for instance, be used to estimate if an over-response of EBT3 films is to be expected for certain irradiation parameters,

or it could also be applied to retrospectively assess if previous experiments were affected by the EBT3 over-response.

One can observe from the trend in figure 10(b) that for intra-pulse dose rates around 1000Gys^{-1} , the parameter m approaches zero. This means that for FLASH experiments using quasi-continuous proton beams with dose rates considerably lower ($\sim 100\text{Gys}^{-1}$) than the intra-pulse dose rates in pulsed UHDR electron beams, as delivered by clinical proton therapy systems based on isochronous cyclotrons, the application of EBT3 films as reference is probably not a problem. This is in agreement with previous studies using UHDR proton beams (Togno *et al* 2022, Horst *et al* 2024). However, at UHDR electron accelerators used for research on the FLASH effect, which typically deliver a few Gy per pulse with intra-pulse dose rates of MGys^{-1} , one should be cautious with EBT3 films and preferably use a different dosimetric reference, e.g. a flashDiamond or alanine. By extrapolating the data presented in this work to other pulsed radiation sources providing even higher intra-pulse dose rates such as laser accelerators (Reimold *et al* 2023), the over-response of EBT3 films may become relevant at doses per pulse even lower than 2 Gy.

Radiochromic films are chemical dosimeters, and therefore the cause for the over-response probably lies in the chemical phase of radiation action (time scale $\sim \mu\text{s} - \text{ms}$) where some mechanism that is not yet fully understood amplifies the polymerization reactions that are responsible for the film darkening (Yasuda *et al* 2025). While the present study focused on EBT3 films, also for EBT-XD films Villoing *et al* (2022) found an over-response in UHDR proton beams and consequently it can be expected that this film will behave similarly. In fact, indications of this have also already been found using UHDR electron beams (Cayley *et al* 2025, Del Sarto *et al* 2025). For the new EBT4 films (Akdeniz 2024) no comprehensive study has been conducted, yet. However, since nothing has changed in the basic functioning principle and chemical composition of these films compared to their predecessors (Miura *et al* 2023) an over-response at UHDR and dose per pulse should be expected for EBT4 as well. Yasuda *et al* (2026) found no indications for an over-response of EBT4 at UHDR but used only a 720Gys^{-1} proton beam for this test.

In addition to the extensive experiments with EBT3 films, also OC-1 films were tested in the present work (see figures 8 and 9). In line with the findings presented by Villoing *et al* (2022), no dose rate dependence was detected in the present experiments. However, it should be pointed out that OC-1 films, besides their proven dose rate independence, have some properties which might be impractical for routine dosimetry in FLASH experiments. We observed, for instance, a strong sheet-by-sheet variation requiring a sheet individual calibration as well as a rather slow darkening after irradiation that takes several days or even weeks. Furthermore, Villoing *et al* (2022) reported an uncertainty for these films up to 13.3% for doses below 10 Gy using the green color channel and their practicality is limited by them not being laminated, making them fragile and difficult to handle. A definite statement concerning the applicability of OC-1 films for routine dosimetry in FLASH experiments would require a more rigorous characterization.

5. Conclusion

The over-response of EBT3 films at ultra high dose rate and dose per pulse was confirmed in experiments at two electron accelerators with different beam pulse structure. For OC-1 films, no dose rate or dose per pulse dependency was detected within the experimental uncertainties which is in agreement with the study by Villoing *et al* (2022). However, the suitability of OC-1 for a practical application as dosimeters in FLASH experiments requires further investigation. The range where EBT3 can safely be applied for FLASH dosimetry is at intra-pulse dose rates below 1kGys^{-1} and doses per pulse up to about 2 Gy. Above that one should expect a significant over-response that depends on the dose per pulse.

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Data availability statement

The data cannot be made publicly available upon publication because they are not available in a format that is sufficiently accessible or reusable by other researchers. The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors.

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